

A review of SSH botnet detection in initial stages of infection: a Machine Learning-based approach

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Abstract—Botnets are exponentially increasing because of new zero-day attacks, a variation of their behavior, and obfuscation techniques that are not detected by traditional defense systems. Botnet detection has been focused on intermediate phases of the botnet’s life cycle during operation, underestimating the initial phase of infection. Using SSH-based High Interaction Honeypots, we have designed a Machine Learning-based system capable of detecting the botnet infection phase in near real time, which was trained with a real dataset of executed commands and the network data obtained during SSH sessions. This approach reached a very high level of prediction and zero false negatives, where all known and unknown SSH sessions aimed at infecting our honeypots were detected.

Index Terms—Botnet, Machine Learning, Zero-day malware, Honeypot, High interaction

Tipo de contribución: *Investigación ya publicada*

I. INTRODUCTION

A botnet is a network composed of hosts (*bots*) infected with malware, which are under human control through Command and Control (C&C) servers, whose life cycle is made up of the infection, communication, and attack phases. In the infection one, the host is infected with malware actively or passively (e.g., vulnerable SSH service or email phishing with a malicious document), through different attack vectors, which are used for downloading the malware binaries that will turn the victim into a potential bot. Secondly, communications take place between the infected computer and the C&C servers in the communication phase, to become a new member of the botnet and to update its behavior. Lastly, in the attack phase, the bots are the ones that carry out the malicious activity (e.g., sensible information theft or DDoS attacks).

The exponential rise in zero-day malware, or its variants that modify their behavior anytime, and the use of advanced obfuscation techniques help the malware to evade the traditional signature- and heuristics-based detection techniques. A practical method for detecting new malware is to use fake and monitored vulnerable systems (or honeypots), and analyze the generated log events to reveal intelligence information and malware behavior on current threats. Besides, the number of attacks is dramatically growing, and analyzing the massive number of log events generated by honeypots is a challenge for security analysts, despite the fact that bots exhibit certain behavioral patterns in their ways of proceeding.

Both facts lead to the current trend of developing bot detection methods based on Machine Learning (ML) techniques, which can recognize complex patterns and make qualified decisions based on experience to detect known and unknown malware with fewer false positives and false negatives, in comparison with other malware detection methods. Several

ML solutions have been defined for botnet detection, but most of them are focused on identifying bots in the communication and attack phases, albeit bots may have caused certain damage. However, a detection during the infection phase would have the advantage that the bot can be identified and disabled before participating in any malicious activity.

To address this, we focused on the development of a novel approach that used ML to detect the infection phase through the SSH service performed by a known or unknown botnet. We focus on SSH because it is a very common botnet attack vector and, to the best of our knowledge, there is no solution focused on the detection of the infection process in SSH-based botnets. The present work was initially published in [1].

II. PROPOSAL

We propose a ML-based solution using Supervised Learning algorithms to automate detection and prediction of incoming SSH security threats aiming to infect new hosts. Thus, our approach needs evaluated and tagged data to build the model and classify the SSH sessions’ behavior, but to the best of our knowledge, there is no public dataset with executed commands and network traffic statistics generated during SSH sessions. We decided to use a high interaction SSH honeypot (HIH) to create a dataset for the effective and dynamic training of our ML model. Fig. 1 depicts the honeypot architecture used in our solution with a *Machine Learning-based Detection System*, in addition to entities such as the *Attacker* and the honeypots unfolding the *SSH Sensors*.

The workflow of our solution starts when an attacker seeks to inject the malware through (default SSH) port 22, breaking into a device through a brute-force or dictionary attack, among others. Malicious SSH behavior conducted by the attackers is captured by our SSH sensors. We focus on the executed commands and the network traffic statistics generated in each SSH session. After the attack, the SSH sensor forwards the captured intelligence information and its self-internal state to the ML-based detection system, where the records received from all SSH sensors are stored in a database. Next, our system generates a new ML-based infection detection model according to the records stored in our database. Finally, the new model is sent to the SSH sensors so that they can update and improve their previous detection model. This process is repeated every day automatically.

Correct labeling of the dataset is essential for an accurate evaluation of results, which is achieved thanks to our honeypots. An SSH session will be tagged as positive when:

- A change in the honeypot status or an outgoing network connection occurs when the attacker logs out.

Fig. 1. The ML-based detection framework for the botnet's infection phase.

- The VirusTotal scanning indicates that the downloaded executable during the session corresponds to a malware.

After five months, we obtained a dataset with 2139 records: 337 positive (infected hosts) and 1802 negative SSH sessions (uninfected hosts). So, the dataset has a total of 93 features: 72 commands, 7 session states, and 14 network statistics. Where *commands* denote a list of different commands executed in all attacks received; *session states* refer to the number of executed commands (namely, Check software configuration, Download a file, Install a program, Run a program, Change the account password, Check the hardware configuration, and Change the system configuration); and *network statistics* are features like session duration, bytes sent, bytes received, etc.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Table I depicts the results obtained by the most widely used ML algorithms in earlier research works. Although Random Forest (RF) and SVM achieve similar results, we chose the RF classifier due to a lower number of false negatives and, mainly, because RF is computationally less expensive.

Model	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1 score (%)
Decision Tree	89.4	100	43.1	60.3
Random Forest	98.1	95.7	93.9	94.8
SVM	97.7	96.7	90.8	93.7
Naive Bayes	69.9	38.2	98.5	55.0

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE OF THE CLASSIFICATION ALGORITHMS PROPOSED.

In the evaluation process, the classification accuracy and other error metrics were used to show the effectiveness of our model, tested with a testing dataset consisting of 427 examples (20% of the dataset): 54 positive SSH sessions (infected hosts) and 373 negative SSH sessions (uninfected hosts).

Our test results are presented in Table II. Not all uninfected SSH sessions were detected, but all malicious SSH sessions were successfully identified (false negatives = 0). Not having false negatives is very critical in an attack detection system.

A thorough analysis of the results shows that network statistics better profile the attacker's behavior than the commands

Class	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1 score (%)
Infected	99.59	96.87	100	98.41
Uninfected	99.59	100	99.53	99.76

TABLE II
MODEL PERFORMANCE FOR OUR TESTING DATASET.

executed by attackers, as shown in Figure 2. Thus, it confirms our hypothesis that commands executed by attackers can give a lot of information about the purpose of the SSH sessions. Still, since several commands are doing the same operation, further context information (e.g., network statistics) is needed to predict attacks accurately. Unfortunately, session states do not seem to represent the infection phase correctly via SSH service. In addition, the most relevant command is *chmod*, widely used to give execution permission to a file to execute it. *Scp* and *wget* allow the transfer and download a file into the victim. Other significant commands are *echo*, *rm*, and *./* (run an executable file). These commands correspond to Download, Installation, and Execution states, a sequence widely used in this attack type. These results do not mean that attackers cannot infect a host executing other commands, but it is the most frequently seen pattern in the received attacks.

Fig. 2. Precision-Recall curve for classification.

As a summary, very positive results were achieved, but no real comparison can be made with other works since existing datasets with network traffic reflect phases other than that of infection and the commands executed by attackers only fit with our scenario. Instead, we have evaluated our approach with a dataset created by our honeypots for an SSH attack environment. Thus, we can confirm that ML techniques are feasible for our detection system.

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